

A Study on Neglected Senior Citizens living in Old Age Homes

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Abstract

There has been rapid aging of the earth's population, and in a few decades, Asia could become the oldest region in the world. Due to the rearrangement of the family system, the popular joint family system is on the decline, in India. Due to the emergence of the atomic family and the high cost of living, family members who earlier cared for the elderly need to find employment outside the home. A rapid increment in nuclear families and an outstanding increment in the number of 'older adults' in the country have enforced them to live in nursing homes. Literature has accentuated the difficulties and apprehensions endured by older adults during the aging process and the need for nursing homes to create an environment that fosters a meaningful existence for them in their twilight years. India's nursing homes are trying to uphold the desires, needs, and values of older adults. There is a shortage of studies that attempt to give older adults a chance to express their practices in a care home. Older adults are an invaluable source for younger periods, and change is required in society's approach towards aging. This report can help psychologists, social workers, and caregivers gain insight into the needs of older adults in terms of mental wellbeing, social security and economical, and elder abuse and create awareness among the people.

Keywords: older adults; nursing homes; aging; experiences.

Introduction

There has a myriad shift in the history of humankind, particularly the rapid aging of the earth's population in recent years. Aging is a natural process, and no human being can leave from this. In the last few years, a bulk of the older adults seem to consider on successful aging, and they define successful aging as multidimensional which encompasses physical, psychological, functional and social health (Phelan et al., 2004).

There are almost 600 million people over the age of 60 living on this planet. By the year 2050, this figure is required to quadruple to two billion (Stone, 2009). A joint report by the UNFPA and Help Age International in 2012 said India has nearly 100 million aged adults and the number is demanded to expand to 323 million by 2050, composing 20 percent of the total population (HelpAge India, 2014).

"Elderly or old age consists of ages surpassing or nearing the average lifespan of human beings. In all societies, the boundary of old age cannot be assigned, especially because it does not have the

same meaning. In the Subsistence and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007, In India, senior citizen means any person being a citizen, who has attained the age of 60 years or above” (Jeyalakshmi et al., 2011).

The aging process is a biological certainty which is largely beyond human control. However, it is also subject to how society makes sense of old age. In the advanced world, chronological time plays a crucial part. The age of 65 or 60 in the generated world is considered the age of leaving and is an implication of the opening of old age. In contrast, in the developing world, different socially produced meanings of age are more outstanding such as the roles assigned to older people. For some, it is the loss of parts that accompany physical decline, which is a defining factor for old age. So, in contrast to historical milestones, which signify life stages in the developed world, in many developing countries, old age begins when active participation and involvement is no longer possible (Gorman, 1999).

In the age of 60 years, the United Nations has defined an older adult as an individual over. However, families and communities often refer to various other socio-cultural looks to determine age such as family status, e.g., grandparents; physical appearance, e.g., grey hair and wrinkles; or health conditions related to age. However, the effects of psychosocial and psychologically traumatic experiences, coupled with poor nutrition and exposure to disease, has led to faster aging in emigrants than settled societies (Atwell et al., 2007).

“In 2011, India has a population of 1.21 billion people. It is the second most populated country in the world, only to China. The UN determines a country as ‘ageing’ where the relationship of people over 60 reaches seven percent. By 2000 India has passed that proportion (7.7%) and is required to reach 12.6% in 2025. By that definition alone, India restrains as an ‘Ageing’ country. An aging population puts an enhanced burden on the support of a country. With more mouths to support and fewer hands to earn, the potency of a country goes down. “Almost 60-75% of all older adults are economically dependent on others, regularly their children. Even those with payments find their economic status lowered after leaving” (Mahajan and Ray, 2013).

Changing Trends in the Indian Family System

The aged population in India is increasing phenomenally in numbers, and at the same time, the size of the family is defeating, especially in the urban areas (HelpAge India, 2013). The joint family system has been prevailing for a long time in India and the children; mainly, the sons cared for their aged parents. Although, in recent times, there has been a change in the family structure, and the usual joint family system is on the decay. With the improvement in nuclear families, Indians are moving out of the normal mode of aging, such, as considering for their aged parents at house. The family system is facing many changes as the physical and mental health of older adults begins to decay, and this has led to the problem of community care for aged parents and the emergence of nursing homes in India (Lamb, 2007).

The family system seems to be encompassing and critiquing western living, and one such move in family life is that a high number of older adults are participating in nursing homes in recent years. As a result, researchers from various fields are giving interest and are researching the changes and effects of this transition on older adults. Though there are no accurate figures for nursing homes in India, their number is expected to be more than 1000. Although, at the same time, it has also been observed that there is a lack of literature that tries to give older adults a chance to express their lived experiences while residing in a care home (Stone, 2009).

Experiences of Older Adults

Often older adults go to nursing homes as they give them security and medical inspection. They may experience isolation, but at the same time, feel a sense of freedom. On the one hand, some of them are required to move to a nursing home because they have experienced lack of enthusiastic support, verbal and at times physical abuse, irreverence, and neglect, from their children. But, often despite this, they seem to favor to be living in the convenience of their own home with their grandchildren and children (Kumar et al., 2012; HelpAge India, 2013; HelpAge India, 2014).

Older adults living in nursing homes face problems of adjustment with tight and rigid schedules; total or near-total separation from their family, society, and friends; fear over entrusting oneself to a new environment; diminished physical capacity and close and regular encounters with death and illnesses in the institution. For many of them, social help is almost absent, and this leaves older adults with the feeling that she or he does not belong, is not loved or worried for, deemed or valued (Kumar et al., 2012). These and other factors make older adults frequently vulnerable to mental health problems and their unwanted effects (HelpAge India, 2013).

Older adults have offensive experiences as they not only have to deal with change in their living conditions but also have to get used to changes in daily life routines and support networks and social. They feel the loss of family and knowledge of loneliness due to the lack of social communications. They also think the experience of powerlessness, and their attention and doubts had adverse effects on their accommodating and settling into a new environment. Often they join the nursing home because of the loss of a spouse, deterioration in health and the incapacity to look after oneself due to physical illness and disability, which leads to increased business problems (Salarvand et al., 2008; Sigaroudi et al., 2013).

Older adults take time to be acclimatized to a new environment when they relocate to an organization, which they have to call home. They take time to adjust to and modify their view of themselves and their environment; they actively show on their life experiences and the struggles they experience and cope with, as this helps them to create an essential existence within the context of a care home. They eventually get wholly involved in the life they are supposed to live. In joining to this, the holistic needs of older adults such as social, mental, financial, spiritual and physical needs are to be considered to promote a purposive and meaningful life for them (Stone, 2009; de Guzman, 2012).

Though older adults seem to find amusement in life across the life cycle, there seems to be a rapid drop in life satisfaction among older adults who are 85 years and above. The reasons being that they experience debilitating health forms; increased risk of fault, functional impairments, and poor health; and this puts limitations on their life satisfaction and also overwhelm them to such an extent that their eloquence of well-being is decreased (Gwozdz & Sousa-Poza, 2010).

With increased frailty and deteriorating health comes the fear of falling, which seems to be a standard charge with older adults. To cope adequately, they learn to discipline their daily lives by studying to accept and live with the challenges of their unsafe and declining physical state and the destruction of control at different levels such as when they drop, from desire and from the stigma of facing an impossible situation. Older adults try to be as free as possible but are also secondary to community care. They cope with their fear of dropping by encouraging their will (Mahler and Sarvima"ki, 2012).

According to social networks and family, research intimates that older adults turn to instant family for particular kinds of assistance and also look to friends staying nearby for alternative sources of help. Older adults also use their social network when they need to charge in and talk to people about health cares but do not seek much help when it comes to household jobs, financial advice or transportation (Phillips et al., 2000)

Conclusion

The rapid extension of the elderly population highlights elder care as a crucial issue in India (HelpAge India, 2013). The problems of earlier security and well-being are converting a matter of interest. There is a need to take care of older adults, with a focus on social and mental well-being, financial and social safety, and elder abuse. Regarding all these factors, there seems to be a need to understand the practices of older adults to adopt powerful mechanisms by which they will be cared for and respected and will be ready to live a life with pride (Kumar et al., 2012).

However, though there is a need to generate awareness among older adults and their families; and caregivers of nursing homes, about the needs, experiences and coping styles of older adults; it would be more beneficial to grant older adults to be emotionally vibrant about living positive and fulfilling lives. This will help to demote the stress and challenges of living in a home and also enable older adults to experience the happiness of living in their twilight years.

A large fraction of older adults is living either in a home for the aged or alone at home without the support of the urgent family. It would be exciting to explore the life experiences and the coping styles of these older adults. The research could also examine if living with family has more meaning for older adults than when living in a community.

We need to admit that residing in a nursing home is stressful and challenging. The ‘old age home’ is no longer a western concept in today India. There are nursing homes in India that are making an effort to uphold the desires, needs, and values of older adults, while also performing and fulfilling new ones (Lamb, 2007).

To facilitate a more meaningful, fulfilling, and gratifying life in older adults, they can be helped to be more positive and confident.

To help this, a particular accent can be laid on Psychological Capital (PsyCap) of the Elderly. It concentrates on the individual’s positive mental power and positive aging and offers a new outlook on how to help older adults live a fulfilling, vibrant life, and happy (Yongmei, 2015). That older adult who live in nursing homes and are lonely and have nearly nothing to look onward to, PsyCap will give them revived confidence and faith in themselves as it focuses on improving mental health by instilling a sense of hope, optimism, self-efficacy, resilience, and wellbeing.

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